

LEARNING THEORIES: REFLECTION DURING ENGLISH CLASSES AT SENIOR SECONDARY LEVEL

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Abstract:

This research paper observes the reflection of various learning theories during actual classroom teaching learning situations by using mixed method approach. The sample used in the study includes students studying in class xi and xii of both CBSE and RBSE affiliated schools and trained teachers teaching at senior secondary level of Jaipur district. The tool used in the study is self-constructed observation schedule.

Keywords: learning theories, English classes, reflection

1. Introduction

Teacher education in India has developed since its introduction in the country at the time of British rule. It developed with each passing year and recognized as a very important aspect in the improvement of overall quality of Indian Education System. UGC model curriculum says that teacher education in India represents a discipline that has chosen to live in past instead of moving ahead and changing with the time. It is yet to develop futuristic thrust that is meaningful in the context emerging, gradually unfolding changes and challenges. This research paper is aimed at investigating the reflection of learning theories during classroom teaching and to find out the practical implication of the training of these theories during classroom teaching. The objective is to study the reflection of learning theories (S-R theories without reinforcement, S-R theories with reinforcement) on teaching - learning process of English teaching at Higher Secondary level.

Who could be a good teacher? Is teaching a quality that a person possesses by birth as a gift of God or it can be acquired? These questions are often debated but are still unanswered. To inculcate the skills of teaching in a person, to make him perfect in

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using various methods to present content to the student, the art of teaching took shape of a separate branch of study in colleges and universities. Extensive research work is undergoing to understand the mysteries of teacher and his behavior during teaching. Many researches indicate that a person needs training before he takes up teaching as a profession. Bhatt, M. M. studied the assumption that qualitative improvement in education was possible by preparing better teachers in training schools. A scheme based on the assumption was developed and tried out at the Government basic Training School, Kapasan. The study revealed that as a result of training, there was improvement in lesson planning and standard of teaching. On the basis of pre and post tests trainees' knowledge of the content was found to be much improved and they were encouraged to teach in a planned manner. Srivastava, M. B. in her evaluation of the impact of training found that it did improve teaching efficiency, which, in turn, influenced the attitude and aptitude of student teachers. It becomes more important, as teacher has to deal with a small society in a class where he find heterogeneous group of students with different socio-cultural background and intelligence level. Kahlon, S. P. and Saini, S. K.'s study was concerned with the impact of teacher education on the aptitude of education graduates of Panjab Agricultural University. The relationship between academic achievement and teaching aptitude was also investigated.

2. Population and Sample

The population constitutes all the teachers who are teaching English subject at higher secondary level and students studying in XI and XII classes in Jaipur District. The total number of trained English teachers teaching in CBSE schools of Jaipur district is 1658 and RBSE schools is 1287.

A sample of 30 higher secondary teachers depending on their teaching experience was selected by random sampling technique for classroom observation.

3. Tool

The selection of tools for a particular study depends upon various considerations such as the objectives of the study, the amount of time, the availability of suitable tests, personal competence of the examinee to administer, score and interpret the test results and the like. Considering these factors carefully, the researcher selected following tools: Observation Schedule (self-constructed).

4. Methodology

To bring out authenticity in the present study it was decided to use Phenomenological (qualitative) approach to observe the reflection of elements of learning theories during English classroom teaching learning situations. Event recording was done by the researcher to observe the use of components of learning theories by the teachers teaching English subject in the senior secondary classrooms.

5. Analysis of reflection of Learning Theories

The primary objective of instruction in school is to bring certain desirable changes in the behaviour of children through the process of learning. The teacher should know the needs and motives of children at different age levels. The researcher thoroughly read learning theories and their implications in classroom. Following behaviors were selected by the researcher to observe the reflection of knowledge of learning theories during English classroom teaching by the trained teachers:

Table 1.1: Elements of Learning Theories in the Observation Schedule

1	Attitude towards students:
	1.1. Collaborative
	1.2. Democratic
	1.3. Unbiased
	1.4. Concerned for student's conduct
2	Logical and systematic presentation of content
3	Giving practice tests to eliminate exam fear
4	Encouraging public speaking by shy students
5	Regular correction work and remedial teaching

The concept of reinforcement is central in operant conditioning theory of Skinner. The two broad categories of reinforcement are positive reinforcement and negative reinforcement. Reinforcers strengthen the behaviour, intensify certain aspects of ensuing behaviour and help in alteration in behaviour. Learning theory of behaviourism can be used to develop certain emotional responses and rectifying others like fears, anxiety etc. examination fear is a common problem that students face. Teacher can give regular practice sets which will eventually eliminate the examination fear. 11 teachers out of 30 used this technique to help the students face exam. A teacher thoroughly friendly with learning theories knows that school activities must be logical in such a way that learner may have some degree of confidence and success in their work. To develop confidence in shy students, it is important to provide them ample opportunities of public speaking. 188 times teachers provided opportunities of public speaking to the students.

Researcher found 10 teachers out of thirty were doing regular correction work and remedial teaching to help students in rectifying their errors.

Figure 1.1: Graphical representation of attitude exhibited by the teachers

11 teachers showed collaborative attitude towards students while rest were not teaching with such attitude. Out of thirty teachers, only two teachers were not showing democratic attitude towards students in class, although all the teachers were unbiased except one teacher who was showing biased attitude.

All the teachers observed by the researcher, except one, found presenting content in logical and systematic way. Teachers used trial and error theory of Thorndike that focuses on satisfactory and pleasant classroom experiences. According to this theory, learning experiences and other activities must be meaningful and understandable. Teacher must present content in logical and systematic way.

Figure 1.2: Pie – diagram showing presentation of content in logical order

Out of thirty teachers observed 11 teachers found giving practice tests to low achievers i.e. 63.3% teachers were not found giving any test assignment to eliminate examination fear.

Figure 1.3: Pie diagram showing frequency of practice test given to eliminate exam fear

More than half of the teachers i.e. 18 teachers out of 30 teachers observed were found doing regular correction during classroom teaching.

Figure 1.4: Pie diagram showing frequency of regular correction work

On the basis of above, observation the researcher found that classroom implications of both S-R theory with reinforcement and S-R theory without reinforcement are useful for teachers as they are abundantly used during classroom teaching – learning. Therefore, the assumption that there is reflection of course of study of learning theories such as S-R theory with reinforcement and S-R theory without reinforcement on teaching learning process of English teaching is proved.

The above observation proves that trained teachers use components of learning theories during classroom teaching learning.

6. Conclusion

During classroom observation, the use of applications of these theories by the teachers was recorded. There are numerous applications of these theories, but a few were commonly used. There are many ways in which a teacher can apply his knowledge of learning theories in classroom as per the needs of the students. The researcher opines that new and creative applications of learning theories need to be included in the syllabus and not only the theoretical aspect but the pedagogical use must also be taken

care of. For example, to recognize the achievement of students throughout the academic year achievers' board can be used in the class on which the photograph and achievement of the student can be displayed throughout the year. This will definitely give a very positive reinforcement to the student to continue the same behaviour and will inspire other students also to do so.

With introduction of CCE system in CBSE affiliated schools, providing grade points to the students can be very effective. There are numerous researches on learning theories having umpteen new applications that can be applied in the classroom teaching. The need is to update the syllabus with the help of the suggestions given in the research works done by the research scholars.

There are two broad categories of schools in India – Hindi medium and English medium. Most of the English medium schools are CBSE affiliated while Hindi medium schools are RBSE affiliated. CBSE schools are considered as the schools using 'modern teaching methods' while RBSE schools are considered as the schools using 'traditional teaching methods'. The skills that are required for effective teaching are broadly based on learning theories. Traditional method of teaching is teacher oriented whereas modern method of teaching is learner centered. Here, there is more emphasis on participatory approach. Learner oriented teaching uses more applications of learning theories as compared to teacher centered teaching

The researcher felt that learning theories must be taught to the pupil teachers extensively during pre-service teacher training. Practice lessons need to be recorded to show the pupil teachers the scope of better utility of applications of learning theories. Not only this, but 'inclusion of innovative methods of use of learning theories' should also be included in the curriculum to make pupil teachers better equipped.

References

1. Baron, Robert A. et.al. *Social Psychology*. Delhi: Dorling Kindersley (India) Pvt. Ltd., 2007.
2. Bentham, Susan. *Psychology and Education*. New York: Routledge, 2002.
3. Bhatnagar, A. B. et al. *Advanced Educational Psychology*. Meerut: International Publishing House, 2007.
4. Bigge, Morris L. *Learning Theories for Teachers*. Delhi: Universal Book Stall, 1967.
5. Chauhan, S. S. *Advanced Educational Psychology*. Noida: Vikas Publishing House Pvt. Ltd., 2007.
6. Creswell. J. W. *Research Design: Qualitative, Quantitative and Mixed Methods Approaches*. 2nd ed. London: Sage, 2003.
7. Freeman, Frank S. *Theory and Practice of Psychological Testing*. New Delhi: Oxford and IBH Publishing Co. Pvt. Ltd., 1962.
8. Hilgard, Ernest R. et al. *Introduction to psychology (6thed.)*. New Delhi: Oxford and IBH Publishing Co. Pvt. Ltd., 1976.

9. Hurlock, Elizabeth B. *Developmental Psychology: A Lifespan Approach*. New Delhi: Tata McGraw – Hill Publishing Co. Ltd., 2006.
10. Johnson, Burke R., & Anthony J. Onwuegbuzie. *Mixed Method Research: A Research Paradigm Whose Time has Come*. *Educational Researcher*, Vol. 33 No. 7 (Oct., 2004).
11. Rather, A. R. *Psychology of Learning and Development*. Discovery Publishing House: New Delhi, 2004.
12. Skinner, Charles E. *Educational Psychology*. New Delhi: Prentice Hall of India Pvt. Ltd., 2005.
13. Storm, Robert D. *Psychology for the Classroom*. New Jersey: Prentice hall Inc., Englewood Cliffs, 1969.
14. Storm, Robert D. *Psychology for the Classroom*. New Jersey: Prentice Hall Inc., 1969.
15. Tashakkori, A., and C. Teddlie. *Mixed Methodology: Combining Qualitative and Quantitative Approaches*. London: Sage, 2002.
16. Woolfolk, Anita and Dorling. *Educational Psychology*. (9th Ed.) New Delhi: Kindersley (India) Pvt. Ltd., 2011.

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